

1 **CARD11 activity during differentiation to the trophectoderm in embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 CARD11 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem
10 cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Ma, C.A., Stinson, J.R., Zhang, Y., Abbott, J.K., Weinreich, M.A., Hauk, P.J., Reynolds, P.R.,
13 Lyons, J.J., Nelson, C.G., Ruffo, E. and Dorjbal, B., 2017. Germline hypomorphic CARD11 mutations in
14 severe atopic disease. Nature genetics, 49(8), pp.1192-1201.